

“INSECTS”
(PRACTICAL LESSON FOR PRESCHOOLERS)

Ashurova Zarina Muxitdinovna

*Bukhara State University Teacher of the
Preschool Education Department of the Pedagogical Institute*

Annotation: The article describes the development of a lesson based on STEAM technology for preschool children.

Keywords: STEAM, tweezers, STEAM set for study, insects,

Educational aspect: To provide general information that "insects" are part of wildlife; learn to distinguish between insects crawling on the ground and flying through the air; conducting practical classes on the structure, habitat and nutrition of insects, awakening a sense of love for nature in the hearts of preschoolers;

Developing aspect: Development of cognitive processes, fine motor skills of children and trust in the team;

Equipment: STEAM set for study living and inanimate nature: tweezers, anthill, insect trap, magnifying glass, insect exhibits.

1. Children will be shown a special film about “Insects”.
2. Repeat with children the types and names of “insects” (picture № 1).

№ 1. “Insects”

3. We go on an excursion with the children with special “tweezers”, attach the “ant” to the “keeper of insects” (pictures № 2-3).

№ 2. Tweezers

№ 3. Keeper of insects

4. Having arrived in the group, we place the “ant” in a special nest for ants and observe it through a magnifying glass (pictures № 4-5).

№ 4. Ant’s nest

№ 5. Magnifying glass

5. After observing the ant through a magnifying glass, study its structure (picture № 6).

№ 6. Anthill

6. After a certain period of time, the ants get used to the new nest and multiply

quickly, and the nest looks like this. (picture № 7). The preschool children watch them every day and prepare reports with the help of the teacher.

7. Place the grasshopper caught during the tour in a “mini-laboratory”. “Mini lab” shows grasshopper 5-6 times its size (picture № 8).

№ 8. Mini laboratory

8. Children of the preparatory group of the school are watching the grasshopper. The teacher gives general information about the structure and nutrition of the grasshopper. (picture № 9)

№ 9. grasshopper

9. Take a grasshopper and put it in a special STEAM container called “Sound Studio” and listen to the “buzz” of a grasshopper through headphones. (picture № 10).

№ 10. "Sound Studio"

10. The butterfly caught during the tour is placed in a special DOUBLE container, called the "butterfly room", and viewed with a 10x magnification behind a magnifying glass that serves as a lid. (picture № 11).

№ 11. "Butterfly room"

11. Children will be informed about the structure, habitat and nutrition of the butterfly. (picture № 12).

№ 12. Butterfly structure

12. A mosquito caught during the excursion is placed in the “Insect Observatory” and examined with a 10x magnification. (picture № 13.).

№ 13. “Insect Observatory”

13. Observing the children, the teacher gives general information about its structure, habitat, nutrition. Children follow the fly and prepare an oral report. (picture №14)

№ 14. The structure of the fly

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